

Light-Weighted Humanoid Robotic Arm Design and Simulation

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Abstract: In this paper, an 8-DoF (with end effector) manipulator is designed and simulated. The 3D model of the humanoid robotic arm is designed in Solidworks (each part is designed separately), and simulation of the manipulator is performed in V-REP software; every part is exported as an STL (stereolithography) file and then imported to simulation software. In the simulation of the robotic manipulator, an inverse kinematic model is developed by using Damped Least Squares (DLS) for calculation. The D-H parameter is used to determine the position and orientation of joints. The experiments have been carried out to show the flexibility, humanoid and smooth movement of robotic manipulator. The robotic manipulator is tested by placing a cuboid on a cuboid in which the stability of the robot is revealed; the pick and place experiment demonstrates flexible movement; the catch the box experiment illustrates the quick response of the robot, which shows the flexible, smooth and humanoid movement of a robotic arm.

Keywords: Humanoid; Robot Arm; V-REP simulation; 8-DOF (with end effector); Inverse Kinematic.

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I. Introduction

The human arm unveils unique skills and flexibility in movement as well as is capable of lifting good loads, which helps to fulfill the basic tasks in daily life [1]. However, robots can help humans as they can work in any circumstance, either in hazardous places or in daily life, to divide their workload and make their lives easier. There is a ton of research on humanoid robotic arms, so the ideal and economical robotic arm can be achieved. Factories and universities use robots either for work or research, but it is still unaffordable for the common man. Some examples of humanoid robot manipulators are as follows: Atlas of Boston Dynamics [2], ASIMO of Honda-Japan [3], and T-HR3 of Toyota-Japan.

It is not easy to design and simulate a humanoid robotic arm because it should resemble the size and features of a human arm [4]. Human arm has distinctive characteristics which is not easy to replicate, lot of tries has been unsuccessful still lot of researches are trying to achieve the smooth, flexible and competent to lifting load [5]. Design is one the essential factor for robotic arm because it should be firm and flexible, we have used SOLIDWORKS software which is friendly interface for 3D drawing. We designed each part separately and exported it in an STL file; once all parts were finalized, we imported them to the Virtual Robot Experimentation Platform (V-REP), which is used for

simulation. Simulation software has made researchers' lives easy as it checks, tests, evaluates and draws graphs for experiments that are carried out in software [6][7].

This paper aims to present the design, simulation, inverse kinematics, D-H parameters, and experiments that show flexible movement with the capability of lifting load.

II. Design

The human arm consists of the shoulder, upper arm, elbow, forearm, wrist, and hand. So, We have designed it according to the human arm; each part is separately made in Solidworks software, which follows Fig. 1, 2. Dimensions are also presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1: Structural design of LWH-Arm

Fig. 2: Parts of LWH-Arm

TABLE 1. Dimension of LWH-ARM.

Parts	Dimension (mm)
Base	43.88
Shoulder	119.99
Arm	133.68
Lower Arm	165.60
Elbow with Forearm	150.99
Wrist	127.63
Total Dimension	741.77

The designed parts are saved in STL (stereolithography) format. The stlparts will carry structure and shape information which will be deliver to simulation software. We use simulation software to check the structure design. The design should be rigid enough so it is capable of lifting the load. Plastic will beadopted to print all parts because of it is light-

weighted and cost effective. If the design is not firm it can crack or break parts of robotic arm. We can check the structure in simulation software and see if any improvement is required to achieve a stable and rigid design so we can make changes in the design.

III. Kinematics

Kinematics deals with the motion of bodies and systems without considering the force and applies geometry to the study movement of multi-DoF kinematic chains that form the structure of a robot manipulator [8]. It shows the relationship between the linkages of the robot with position, orientation, and acceleration. The robotic kinematic is divided into two types: forward kinematic and inverse kinematic[9][10].

A. Forward and Inverse Kinematic

The DLS mode plots the kinematics configuration of each joint. Dummies are added at the base and tip of a robotic arm to specify the kinematic chain. The joint servos are enabled as inverse kinematics. The inverse kinematic API of V-REP computes the kinematic chain to perform an action of the robotic arm.

B. Damped Least Squares Method (DLS)

It is also known as the Levenberg-Marquardt method; the DLS method avoids many of the pseudoinverse method's problems with singularities and can give a numerically stable method of selecting $\Delta\theta$ [11]. Rather than just finding the minimum vector that offers the best solution to $e = J\theta\Delta$, we find the value that minimizes the quantity.

$$\|J\Delta\theta - \vec{e}\|^2 + \lambda^2\|\Delta\theta\|^2 \quad (1)$$

Where $\lambda \in R$ is a non-zero damping constant. This is equivalent to minimizing the quantity

$$\left\| \begin{pmatrix} J \\ \lambda I \end{pmatrix} \Delta\theta - \begin{pmatrix} \vec{e} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\| \quad (2)$$

The corresponding normal equation is: $\begin{pmatrix} J \\ \lambda I \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} J \\ \lambda I \end{pmatrix} \Delta\theta = \begin{pmatrix} J \\ \lambda I \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \vec{e} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$ (3)

This can be equivalently rewritten as $(J^T J + \lambda^2 I) \Delta\theta = J^T \vec{e}$ (4)

It can be shown that $J^T J + \lambda^2 I$ is non-singular. Thus, DLS solution is equal to

$$\Delta\theta = (J^T J + \lambda^2 I)^{-1} J^T \vec{e} \quad (5)$$

Now $J^T J$ is a $n \times n$, where n is the number of degree of freedom. It is easy to show that $(J^T J + \lambda^2 I)^{-1} J^T = J^T (J J^T + \lambda^2 I)^{-1}$. Thus,

$$\Delta\theta = J^T (J J^T + \lambda^2 I)^{-1} \vec{e} \quad (6)$$

The advantage of eq. (6) with the previous one is matrix being inverted $m \times m$ where $m=3k$ is the dimension of the space of target positions, and m is often much less than n . Eq. (6) can also be computed without needing to carry out the matrix inversion, instead row operation can find \vec{f} such that $(J J^T + \lambda^2 I) \vec{f} = \vec{e}$ and then $J^T \vec{f}$ is the solution.

The damping constant depends on details of multibody and target place, which should be chosen carefully to make Eq. (6) numerically stable. The constant should be large enough so the solution for Δ

θ is well-behaved near singularities, but if chosen too large, then the convergence rate is too slow. Many methods have been proposed for selecting damping constants dynamically based on configuration of articulated multibody.

C. D-H parameters

It was introduced by Jacques Denavit and Richard S. Hartenberg, known as D-H parameters. D-H convention selects a frame of reference for the robotic arm. In this coordinate, frames are attached to the joints between two links to describe the location of each link relative to its previous one[12] Fig. 3.

Four parameters are used in the D-H parameter representation, as shown in Table 2. These parameters describe the relative rotation and translation between consecutive frames: θ_i indicates the angle variable of joint i , d_i indicates the line offset distance of each joint axis, a_i indicates the offset distance of link i , α_i indicates the axis angle between joint i and joint $i-1$.

Fig. 3: D-H parameter of LWH-Arm

TABLE 2. D-H parameters of LWH-ARM.

Joint	θ_i (variable)	d_i (m)	a_i (m)	α_i (degree)
Shoulder	θ_1	L1	0	$\pi/2$
Upper Arm	θ_2	0	0	0
Lower Arm	θ_3	0	L2	0
Elbow	θ_4	0	L3	0
Forearm	θ_5	0	0	$-\pi/2$
Wrist	θ_6	0	0	$\pi/2$
Lower Wrist	θ_7	L4	0	$\pi/2$

IV. Modelling manipulator in V-REP

With an integrated development environment, the robot simulator V-REP is based on a distributed control architecture. The script in V-REP is the main control mechanism for simulation and is handled when the client application calls the main script. The objective is to import all stl files individually and assemble them to make a robotic manipulator. In V-REP, the parts are connected by links and joints.

A. Import and Assembling the parts in V-REP

The steps for assembling the robotic manipulator are as follows: import STL files into the main scene and then rename all the imported components according to shape. The components are individually placed first, and then, using the manipulation toolbar button, the part is adjusted by rotating or translating parts. Joints (revolute and prismatic) can be added to each link and positioned according to it, as shown in Fig 4.

Fig. 4: Import files and assembling

B. Configuring the IK Module

After the assembly of the manipulator and molding of the structure in the hierarchy scene, the inverse kinematics module is defined. First, enable the joints in IK mode. After enabling joints, add the target and tip dummy to the scene, position them accordingly, and specify a target to follow. Also, link the dummy target with the tip. Linking the dummies in the scene a red colored line will appear in the hierarchy scene indicating the dummy object that have linked together. Add a new IK group and IK element, choosing the calculation method (DLS method), defining a path for movement and adding a script after which can simulate the scene, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: IK mode with DLS method

V. Experiment and evaluation

The robotic manipulator arm was linked and joined together. A total of 8-DoF (with end effector) was modeled, and the script was written to achieve the target. To verify the flexibility and effectiveness of the robotic manipulator, we designed a scene and ran experiments in V-REP simulation software.

A. Placing cuboid on cuboid

Placing a cuboid on a cuboid in this simulation example, we have a convey belt with two cuboids placed on it. Convey-belt has a proximity sensor attached to it. The sensor's purpose is to stop the rotation of the convey belt if it detects the cuboid. Placing a cuboid on a cuboid is a process of clutching a cuboid placed on a convey belt with a proximity sensor. Once the cuboid reaches the sensor, the convey belt will stop moving, and the robotic arm's end effector will reach the cuboid's position. The end effector then will grasp the cuboid and lift it, moving it to the target position and placing it at the target position by opening the end effector. Once the cuboid is placed at the target, the end effector will return to grasp another cuboid, grasp the second cuboid, and place it on top of the first cuboid. After that, the robotic manipulator

will return to its starting position, and the simulation will end, as shown in Fig. 6, 7, 8. The End effector is stable while placing the cuboid without affecting the first one, demonstrating the robotic arm's stability.

Fig. 6: Placing cuboid on cuboid

Fig. 7: Joint position

Fig. 8: Joint force

B. Pick and Place

Pick and place in this simulation: We have a convey belt with four cuboids on top of it. It also has a proximity sensor on it whose purpose is to detect the cuboid that will stop the belt rotation. When the belt is stopped, the end effector will move toward the direction of the cuboid, grasp the cuboid, and lift it. After lifting the cuboid, the end effector will move towards the target position. Once the end effector reaches the target place, it will release the cuboid and return to pick another cuboid. Each time, the end effector will place the cuboid and move it to the target place specified in the script. Once all the cuboid is placed on the target place, the robotic arm will return to its starting position, and the simulation will stop running, as shown in Fig. 9. The target position is configured in the script, which can be changed. This experiment illustrates a robotic arm's flexible and smooth movement while placing four cuboids Fig. 10, 11.

Fig. 9: Pick and place

Fig. 10: Joint position

Fig. 11: Joint force

C. Catch the box

Catch the box. In this simulation, we have the box, robotic manipulator, and proximity sensor. The box is lifted in height and released for there, once the box cross proximity sensor the end effector will start closing the gripper. The end effector will grasp the box, and after that, the end effector will move toward the target place. Once the robotic manipulator reaches the target, it will release the box on the target place, which will be on the table; after releasing the box, the robotic arm will move back to the starting position, as shown in Fig. 12. Quick and fast response is seen in this experiment where the end effector grasps the box and place on the table. Graph reading are shown in Fig. 13, 14.

Fig. 12: Catch the box

Fig. 13: Joint position

Fig. 14: Inverse kinematic

VI. Conclusion

The objective of this project is to design, model, and analyze an 8-DoF humanoid robotic manipulator that is flexible and capable of lifting loads. 3D-designed STL files were imported to simulation software, where they were linked together by adding joints. The simulation is carried out to check the performance of the design. The simulation has been successfully carried out and verify the feasibility and effectiveness of robotic manipulator model. The results clearly show that the model performs all operations very effectively without any sudden or unaccounted movement discontinuity.

The experiments demonstrate the humanoid, smooth, and flexible movements of the robotic arm; for future work, all parts will be printed by a 3D printer and then assembled. It will be tested to verify humanoid characteristics, and changes can be made in the design to achieve the ideal structure.

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